

A Comprehensive Guide to Medical Imaging, Analysis, and Measurement with MATLAB (Advancing Healthcare Through DICOM)

Sabbir Mahamud
Dept. of Biomedical Engineering
Jashore University Of Science And
Technology
191922.bme@student.just.edu.bd
sabbirabir61@gmail.com

Abstract

Medical imaging plays a crucial role in modern healthcare, aiding in diagnosis, treatment planning, and research endeavors. Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) has emerged as the standard format for storing and sharing medical images across various imaging devices and software platforms. This comprehensive guide explores the application of DICOM in advancing healthcare, focusing on medical imaging, analysis, and measurement using MATLAB tools.

The workflow of DICOM, from imaging procedures to data analysis, is outlined, highlighting the seamless transmission and storage of medical imaging data through DICOM servers. Various medical imaging machines supporting DICOM are discussed, ranging from MRI and CT scanners to X-ray and ultrasound devices.

The DICOM Explorer, implemented in MATLAB, facilitates accurate measurement of physical distances, angle determination, and 3D image reconstruction from CT scans. The basic theory behind the DICOM Explorer, including pixel spacing, slice spacing, and Euclidean distance calculations, is elucidated to provide a foundational understanding.

Applications of DICOM-based medical image analysis include fracture analysis, tumor size

estimation, orthopedic planning, cardiac dimension analysis, and pediatric growth assessment, among others. Limitations such as segmentation challenges and compatibility issues are also addressed.

The development of MATLAB tools for medical image measurement represents a significant advancement in healthcare, enabling precise and efficient analysis across various imaging modalities. Accessing medical image data is discussed, with references to prominent databases such as TCIA, Kaggle, and OASIS.

Introduction

DICOM, short for Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine. It's a standard format used for storing and sharing medical images, like X-rays, MRIs, and CT scans. It ensures compatibility between different imaging equipment and software. DICOM allowing healthcare professionals and doctors to easily access and exchange patient images across various systems. Also, patient can examine their data all over the world.

More than hundreds of thousand medical imaging device use DICOM format to export their imaging information. Actually it's a alternative of X-ray film in digital form. You can see your data in 3D form, analysis images. This help to breast cancer detection, fracture length measurement, cardiac stress testing, etc.

The workflow of DICOM (From imaging procedure to data analysis)

In a typical scenario, when a patient undergoes a medical imaging procedure such as a CT scan at a hospital, a radiographer collects relevant patient details, including name, age, and gender, and inputs this information into a computer system. The medical imaging data obtained from the procedure is then formatted according to the DICOM standard, which ensures compatibility and interoperability across different imaging devices and software systems.

Once saved in DICOM format, the data is automatically transmitted or uploaded to a DICOM server, such as data.midrc.org. These DICOM servers act as centralized repositories for medical imaging data, facilitating storage, retrieval, and sharing of images and associated patient information.

Healthcare professionals, such as doctors and researchers, can access this data through DICOM viewers, specialized software applications designed to interpret and display DICOM images. These viewers enable detailed analysis and interpretation of medical images, aiding in diagnosis, treatment planning, and research endeavors.

Platforms like data.midrc.org host vast repositories of medical imaging data, encompassing millions of patient studies. Such repositories play a crucial role in advancing medical research, enabling large-scale data analysis, and facilitating collaboration among healthcare professionals worldwide.

Which medical imaging machine support DICOM?

- MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging)
- CT (Computed Tomography) scanners
- X-ray
- Ultrasound
- Nuclear medicine imaging devices
- Radiation therapy machines
- Optical coherence tomography (OCT)
- Fiber-optic and rigid-scope endoscopy
- Light microscopy for anatomic pathology
- Fluoroscopy

- Angiography

DICOM Explorer

Accurate measurement of physical distances, including bone fractures, tumor sizes, and organ dimensions, using MATLAB tools. Precise determination of angles between anatomical structures for surgical planning and diagnosis.

Also, Successful implementation of 3D measurements in CT-type medical images, providing comprehensive spatial information for medical analysis.

Basic theory behind the DICOM explorer

In medical imaging, pixel spacing refers to the physical distance between adjacent pixels in an image, while slice spacing represents the distance between consecutive image slices along the z-axis. These parameters are essential for accurate measurement calibration in medical image analysis.

To calculate the distance between two points in a medical image, we can use the Euclidean distance formula

For 2D,

$$D_p = \sqrt{((x_2 - x_1) * Px)^2 + ((y_2 - y_1) * Py)^2}$$

For 3D,

$$D_p = \sqrt{((x_2 - x_1) * Px)^2 + ((y_2 - y_1) * Py)^2 + ((z_2 - z_1) * S)^2}$$

Here, pixel spacing in x and y direction denote P_x and P_y respectively and S is slice spacing or thickness and D_p is physical distance between two points.

Additionally, angle measurements can be determined using the cosine rule:

$$\cos\theta = \frac{a^2 + b^2 - c^2}{2ab}$$

where θ represents the angle between two line segments, and a , b , and c denote the lengths of the line segments.

Creating 3D images from CT scans involves precise data collection and computational techniques. Initially, high-quality slice data is obtained from a CT scanner, with careful consideration given to parameters like slice thickness and spacing.

These slices are then processed to generate a 3D matrix called a voxel grid, where each voxel corresponds to a small volume element within the scanned object. Calibration and adjustment of parameters such as slice thickness and spacing are crucial for accurate reconstruction.

This systematic approach ensures the fidelity and utility of 3D images derived from CT scans, facilitating enhanced medical diagnostics and treatment planning.

Workflow

DICOM Overview

Figure: DICOM EXPLORER

Figure: X-Ray Image of Tibia (Measure length ~ 382 mm)

Figure: Angle determination of joint

Figure: Area measurement using Ellipse & Rectangle shape

Figure: CT image of Humerus viewed in 3D from ~400 slices

Figure: 3D views of Humerus

Figure: CT image of Upper part of humerus, right one measure length in 3D plane and left one is single slice measurement

Figure: Xray image with pre known length marker (Marker length ~50mm)

Application

Fracture Analysis: Accurately measure the length of bone fractures using MATLAB's measurement tools. Quantify the severity of fractures to aid in treatment planning and monitoring.

Tumor Size Estimation: Determine the size of tumors in medical images using ruler and circle detection algorithms. Provide oncologists with precise measurements for assessing tumor growth and response to treatment.

Orthopedic Planning: Measure bone length, alignment angles, and joint space widths to assist orthopedic surgeons in surgical planning. Improve the accuracy of orthopedic procedures such as joint replacement and fracture fixation.

Cardiac Dimension Analysis: Quantify heart chamber sizes and wall thicknesses in cardiac imaging studies. Assist cardiologists in diagnosing cardiac conditions and evaluating heart function.

3D Measurement in CT Images: Perform three-dimensional measurements of anatomical structures in

CT-type medical images. Enhance spatial visualization and analysis for comprehensive diagnostic assessment.

Angle Determination for Surgical Planning: Use MATLAB's angle measurement tools to determine the angle between anatomical structures. Aid surgeons in planning surgical approaches and assessing anatomical relationships.

Tumor Localization and Characterization: Accurately localize tumors within medical images and characterize their morphology. Provide radiologists and oncologists with valuable information for treatment planning and prognosis assessment.

Trauma Assessment: Measure the extent of traumatic injuries, such as fractures and soft tissue damage. Assist emergency physicians and trauma surgeons in triaging and prioritizing patient care.

Vascular Morphometry: Analyze blood vessel dimensions and flow patterns to assess vascular health. Guide interventions for conditions such as atherosclerosis and aneurysms.

Pediatric Growth Assessment: Monitor pediatric growth and development by measuring bone lengths and organ dimensions. Support pediatricians in assessing growth abnormalities and monitoring treatment response.

Limitation

Segmentation of anatomical structures from medical images can be challenging, particularly in cases of complex anatomy or pathologies. Inaccurate segmentation may lead to errors in measurements.

The MATLAB application may have limited compatibility with certain medical image formats or imaging modalities, restricting its applicability across all types of medical images.

The current version of the application may require manual intervention for fine-tuning measurements or correcting segmentation errors, leading to increased time and effort for analysis.

The measurement algorithms used in the application may be sensitive to variations in image characteristics, such as contrast or brightness, potentially affecting the consistency of measurements.

Processing time for analyzing large or high-resolution medical images, especially in three-dimensional analysis, may be significant, limiting the real-time applicability of the application in certain clinical settings.

Required MATLAB V.2024 to run

Discussion

The development of MATLAB tools for medical image measurement represents a significant advancement in the field of healthcare. By leveraging the DICOM standard, which ensures interoperability and compatibility across different imaging modalities, these tools facilitate precise and efficient analysis of medical images, including X-rays, MRIs, and CT scans.

One of the key features of the MATLAB app is its ability to accurately measure physical distances in both 2D and 3D medical images. By considering pixel spacing and slice spacing, the app enables clinicians to calibrate measurements and obtain reliable quantitative data. This functionality is particularly valuable in various clinical scenarios, such as determining the size of tumors, assessing bone fractures, and evaluating organ dimensions.

With the ability to calculate distances using the Euclidean distance formula, the app provides clinicians with essential information for diagnosis, treatment planning, and monitoring of medical conditions.

Moreover, the app facilitates angle measurements using the cosine rule, allowing clinicians to determine the angles between anatomical structures with precision. This capability is crucial for surgical planning, as it enables surgeons to assess the orientation and alignment of structures within the body.

By accurately measuring angles, clinicians can anticipate potential challenges during surgical procedures and develop optimal approaches to achieve successful outcomes. Furthermore, the app's implementation of 3D measurements in CT-type medical images enhances spatial analysis and provides comprehensive information for medical evaluation.

By extending measurement capabilities into the third dimension, clinicians can gain a more thorough understanding of anatomical structures and spatial relationships.

This functionality is particularly beneficial for complex cases where three-dimensional visualization is essential for accurate diagnosis and treatment planning.

How to use DICOM Explorer?

To install MATLAB App Installer (mlappinstall) apps, you typically follow these steps. To download this app simply [click here](#)

1. Download the App Installer Package to your computer.
2. Launch MATLAB on your computer.
3. Navigate to the Apps Tab
4. In MATLAB, navigate to the "APPS" tab on the MATLAB desktop toolbar.
5. Click on the "Install App" button in the APPS tab. This will open a dialog box for installing apps.
6. In the dialog box, browse to the location where you downloaded the .mlappinstall package.
7. Select the .mlappinstall file and click "Open" or "Install".

MATLAB will install the app package. Wait for the installation process to complete. You may see progress indicators or status messages during this time. Access the Installed App:

Once the installation is complete, the app will be available in the APPS tab of MATLAB. You can launch the app from here or search for it using the

MATLAB search bar. Otherwise follow the details guide [here](#).

How to access Medical Image Data?

Accessing medical image data can depend on various factors, including your specific needs, resources, and legal considerations.

- The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA)
- Medical Imaging Databank in Kaggle
- Open Access Series of Imaging Studies (OASIS)
- Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI)
- Image Data Resource (IDR)

Conclusion

Our MATLAB application represents a significant advancement in the field of medical image analysis. By providing healthcare professionals with precise measurement tools for analyzing medical images, project aim to improve diagnostic accuracy, treatment planning, and patient outcomes.

Moving forward, continued advancements in medical imaging technology and computational tools will further enhance the capabilities of these measurement tools, empowering clinicians with powerful resources for precision medicine.

Medical Imaging Database Links

- <https://data.midrc.org/resource-browser>
- <https://isbweb.org/data/vsj/>
- <https://www.aylward.org/notes/open-access-medical-image-repositories>
- <https://nbia.cancerimagingarchive.net/nbia-search/>

Ref.

- <https://dicom.innolitics.com/>
- https://dicom.nema.org/dicom/cp/CPack-36_PDF/cp626_lb.pdf
- <https://forum.dcmk.org/>
- <https://www.rubomedical.com/>